

INSTRUMENTALIZATIONS OF RELIGION & FREEDOM OF RELIGION OR BELIEF: A TOOL FOR NATIONAL INTERESTS OR A UNIVERSAL VALUE?

GANOUNE DIOP¹

The core questions for our reflection are the following:

1. Can a universal human right, freedom of religion or belief, be part of the instruments states or governments use to advance their national interests and global agendas?
2. Should the global arena be ideologically framed to reflect one model of social arrangements such as democracy, capitalism, and liberalism?
3. Is religious freedom only viable in a liberal democratic social arrangement?

The active and global promotion of religious freedom is a relatively new phenomenon. During the age of empire building, conquests, colonialism, slavery, and legitimization of the racialization and divisions of people into superiors and inferiors, religious freedom was not considered a universal value. A step in the right direction while incomplete and filled with contradictions came with the adoption of the legal principle of “Cuius Regio, Eius Religio” (Whose realm, their religion).” In other words, those who rallied around or simply shared the religion of the ruler were allowed the freedom to live in that ruler’s region.

The center for valuation and decisions was not the human person per se but rather the central and exclusive authority and power of the ruler. Something external to human conscience was to dictate the religion (s) of those ruled.

At that point in time, the imperative of autonomous conscience was not part of the non-negotiable nomenclature of universal principles. The quests for and reality of domination, dominance, and dominion overrode rights, that is human rights. Force was not principally an instrument to mitigate and keep in check abusive impulses of turning human beings into conquerable domains. Instead, it was mostly used as an instrument of coercion, subjugation, subjection, submission, and appropriation of indigenous lands, resources, and persons. In

¹ Ganoune Diop, PhD, is Secretary General of the International Religious Liberty Association and Director of Public Affairs and Religious Liberty for the Seventh-day Adventist Church’s World Headquarters. He also serves as Secretary of the Conference of Secretaries of Christian World Communions.

those contexts, humans were considered domains to domesticate. That logic presided over the phenomena and devastating traumas of conquest, colonialism, and empire-building, forced labor, and slavery. It has continued in the current era of coloniality.

Another trajectory began to take shape while the logic of domination, oppression, and exploitation continued to prevail. Religious freedom became an incontrovertible part of the nomenclature of rights and particularly when it became fashionable to recognize it as part of the fundamental freedoms. Nonetheless, it too, saw its scope shrink. It became an instrument to advance national interests. Indeed, at a national level, the step to integrate the project of government promotion of freedom of religion or belief became part of the framework of foreign policy thinking. It became part of a program to turn nations into liberal democracies, this was, so goes the argument, the only way human rights would be respected. In other words, in part of Western political thought, it is widely believed that liberal democracies are the only framework for the flourishing of rights. This belief has been challenged in many ways, precisely because of the instrumentalization of freedom of religion or belief and its use as a tool for national interests and foreign policy.

The instrumentalization of religious freedom has been preceded by the instrumentalization of religion. There seems to be not one major world religious tradition that has escaped the impulse of yearning for world dominance. After all, empire building has been the right arm of world religions, including the stated infamous “mission civilisatrice.”

The instrumentalization of religion is one face of the same coin. The other is the instrumentalization of people. This instrumentalization of people was also accompanied and endorsed by the instrumentalization of religion. No religious tradition has been immune from this form of religious violence.

A little digression may be in order.

It is of interest to note that IRLA started as a resistance movement against the concept of a Christian nation and against the imposition of a mandatory day of worship. From its inception, Christianity claims to be a universal movement, not just a national one, whether Jewish or non- Jewish people.

In the American context, the four freedoms, the freedom of speech and expression, freedom of worship, freedom from want, and freedom from fear, were understood as universal values. (Reference is often made to President Franklin D. Roosevelt, who articulated the so-called Four Freedoms on Monday, January 6, 1941.)

The commitment to freedom has been fret with contradictions and inconsistencies. The key question undergirding the issue is the following:

“How can freedom be compatible with coercion or compulsion in matters of belief and faith? Obviously, international law has provisions for limitations of freedom of religion or belief. The distinction between forum Internum and forum Externum especially in the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) is well known.

During the COVID pandemic, Government prohibitions to gather in churches have triggered complaints according to which the government has no right to restrict peoples’ freedom of religion, especially freedom of assembly. This is misinformed. Suffice it to say that there are two aspects inherent to freedom of religion or belief according to international law: the *Forum Internum* and the *Forum Externum*.

The Forum Internum should never be violated. It is a person’s right to form, to hold and to change beliefs and convictions. This should have absolute protection. However, the *forum externum*, a person’s right to manifest or to outwardly display, one’s religion or belief can be legally subjected to limitations. This aspect of religious freedom is not absolute.

The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights Article 18 (3), specifies:

“Restrictions on the freedom to manifest religion or belief only if limitations are prescribed by law and are necessary to protect public safety, order, health or morals, or the fundamental rights and freedoms of others.”²

During pandemics, therefore, it is a matter of public health and safety to limit freedom of assembly.

One would wish that, with this provision allowing governments to set limitations to freedom to express one’s beliefs in association and assembly with others, for example, that religious freedom is reasonably employed for the public or even universal good. However, there has been more to state relations with religious freedom as repeated government restrictions to religious freedom have shown.

The impulse or urge to dominate which has characterized the inhumanity of humans had made the relations between government and freedom of religion or belief a complex and complicated story. The legitimization of violence finds its roots in the fact that at times ends justify the means. Political expediency and disregard of the principle of separation of church and state or religion and state, have stifled the fundamental and moral imperative position of freedom of religion and belief.

Moreover, when the legitimization of violence is accepted as necessary for survival, and the interests and security of powerful conquerors are branded as

² ICCPR Art. 18 (3).

providential, the door is open for the appropriation of resources, the decimation of populations and displacement of vulnerable people groups not powerful enough to defend themselves and secure their survival. This deep injustice and the fear of being overcome in wars, led nations to arm themselves with the assumption according to the more powerful they become the less likely they will be vulnerable to invasions. Moreover, this logic of self-protection is what is behind the proliferation of nuclear weapons. Nations that have them feel a sense of immunity in not risking being attacked.

But the harm done to people, their land, and resources, is too well documented. How to live with such devastating abuses in every corner of the world, subsequent to the 14th-century *pestilentia* which according to accounts decimated one-third of the European population. The age of exploration at the dawn of the Renaissance changed the global landscape forever. The so-called age of discovery translated into an age of disasters for conquered populations. Moreover, the industrial era added devastating overexploitation of earth's ecosystems. The world today bears the brunt of the ushering of the Anthropocene.

The root causes of major current world crises and predicaments are inseparable from the injustices of instrumentalization and use and abuse of people and of nature for profit and greed to the detriment of dignity and decency. No field of human experiment has been out of the scope of being instrumentalized. Freedom of religion or belief is no exception to being instrumentalized.

Could it be that it was partly to soothe consciences guilty of inflicting so much pain, suffering, and death on indigenous people, people of African descent, and people of color (BIPOC) that the “mission civilisatrice” was invented?

To be fair, the genocides of indigenous people, the domestication, and subjugation of BIPOC after the “Pestilencia” according to several experts' historians decimated one-third of the European population³, had mainly economic reasons. Human rights were not part of a global agenda in any fashion or form.

Freedom of religion or belief is in fact a deterrent to the instrumentalization of human beings. It goes against violence against human beings because they choose to believe according to the dictates of their conscience. Human beings are to be respected. Renouncing violence against people is a moral imperative.

³ The so-called bubonic plague is mostly known in connection to the fourteen-century black death (1346-1353). It began in 1331 in China, but care should be taken not to incriminate Asians indiscriminately and unjustly. This is misinformed and evil. Along with the civil war of the time, the bubonic plague decimated half of the population of China². It was caused by a strain of bacteria. In Europe, one third of the European population is estimated to have died from the plague.

There is a needed circumspection before the mystery of every person. This is prompted by the sacredness of human conscience, the faculty without which our humanity remains incomplete.

The instrumentalization of freedom of religion or belief is similar, not identical but like the use and abuse of blasphemy laws. Blasphemy laws were introduced in central Asia during the British empire. They were subsequently Islamized in a few nations.

On the other spectrum of ideological choices for governance and social contracts, religious freedom is used by governments and reduced to being one of the tools to promote their national interests, agendas. In this perspective, the focus is not on the human person everywhere but on national ideologies, interests, and priorities.

Given the interrelatedness, the interdependency, and the indivisibility of human rights and of fundamental freedoms, the instrumentalization of freedom of religion of belief affects all the other freedoms. It affects the human person at his or her core being which is inseparable from the prerequisite of freedom for human life to flourish.

Governments are set to protect people and their rights. They are entitled to set boundaries within which citizens can assume their legal responsibilities. Separation of religion and state should exclude the infringement of the state in the conscience and beliefs of citizens. States should not legislate religion, except in the case of the external expression of religion in the public space to protect citizens from harm and danger. In times of pandemics, restrictions of the forum externum of religious freedom are entirely conceivable and legal according to international law.

Religious freedom is a guarantee and a reminder of the humanity of every human person. It is a deterrent against the instrumentalization of human beings. It is also an antidote against control, power, and domination of human beings. Human dignity and human rights are inextricably linked to this incontrovertible freedom of thought, conscience, religion, or belief.